

Funding of African research according to funding acknowledgements in Dimensions data

Jonathan Dudek^{*}, Jeroen van Honk^{**}, Isabel Basson^{***}, Carole de Bordes^{**}, Ismael Rafols^{**}
and Rodrigo Costas^{****}

^{*} *j.dudek@cwts.leidenuniv.nl*

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2031-4616>

Centre for Science and Technology Studies (CWTS), Leiden University, The Netherlands

^{**} *j.s.van.honk@cwts.leidenuniv.nl, c.a.m.de.bordes@cwts.leidenuniv.nl, i.rafols@cwts.leidenuniv.nl,*

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1115-3032>, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1773-0259>,

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6527-7778>

Centre for Science and Technology Studies (CWTS), Leiden University, The Netherlands

^{***} *ibasson@sun.ac.za*

<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6150-3208>

Centre for Research on Science and Technology (CREST), Stellenbosch University, South Africa

^{****} *rcostas@cwts.leidenuniv.nl*

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7465-6462>

Centre for Science and Technology Studies (CWTS), Leiden University, The Netherlands

DSI-NRF Centre of Excellence in Scientometrics and Science, Technology and Innovation Policy, Stellenbosch University, South Africa

Abstract

Most African countries have low domestic research funding and receive a significant portion of their funding from foreign sources. Consequently, it is of interest to get a better understanding of funding going to and its influence on African research. The Dimensions (by Digital Science) database provides a wealth of information on publications, including records of funding acknowledgements. In this study, we investigate funding as indicated on publications with African affiliations and address the following questions: Who are the main funders? Which countries do they support? Which scientific fields do they prioritize? As main results, we find regional differences in terms of the funding reported in scientific publications; a strong presence of international funders; and a relatively strong presence of publications with funding information in the Biomedical and health sciences and the Life and earth sciences.

1. Introduction

The research systems of African countries have a significant dependence on international collaboration and funding, which is likely to affect their research agendas. This dependency is particularly relevant because large international funders include philanthropic foundations whose priorities do not necessarily respond to local public priorities or global scientific communities (Vessuri, 2017).

The analysis of research funding is an emerging topic in science and technology studies, both due to the growing interest in understanding the effects of specific instruments in science (Lepori et al., 2023) and due to the desire to prioritize research towards social needs and aspirations (Ciarli & Ràfols, 2019; Sarewitz & Pielke, 2007), especially towards the Sustainable Development Goals (Ciarli et al., 2022). The interest in understanding the influence of investments in science towards well-being is particularly important in developing societies with large social inequalities.

This study explores funding to African countries. Here, we present preliminary findings based only on the mentions of funders in the acknowledgement sections of publications, as recorded in the Dimensions database (Herzog et al., 2020).

The following research questions are addressed in this exploratory work:

- 1) What is the number and share of African publications reporting funding? Are there differences across African countries?
- 2) Who are the main funders in Africa? How do their funded publications behave in terms of collaboration patterns?
- 3) What is the overall disciplinary presence of funding and funders on the continent? Are top funders specialized in certain disciplines?

2. Review of studies using funding acknowledgement data

The quantitative analysis of funding acknowledgements (FA) has become a major research line in the STI and scientometric literature over the past few years, with topics ranging from discussions around the coverage and reliability of FA information (Paul-Hus et al., 2016; Kokol & Vošner, 2018; Liu et al., 2020), to the relationship of the presence of funding and specific funders in publications with citation impact or collaboration patterns, among other topics (Álvarez-Bornstein & Montesi, 2020). In a past study (Kozma et al., 2018), a comprehensive funding landscape was provided for all African countries using the Web of Science (Science Citation Index Expanded - SCIE) as a database for the period 2009 to 2014. The new contribution of the study at hand is the analysis of funding acknowledgements in publications with African participation based on data from Dimensions.

3. Data and Methods

For this study, we used a version of the Dimensions database available in-house at CWTS, last updated in July 2023. This included data on publications, the funding acknowledgements mentioned on publications, and the publications' affiliations. The period of analysis goes from 2010 up to and including 2021. Given the descriptive nature of this analysis and the fact that no citation analysis is performed in this study, we have included all document types captured by Dimensions. Publications were included on the basis of at least one affiliation with an African country. The geographical spectrum of the countries analysed includes the 58 African countries (continent='AF'), identified by their ISO-3166 alpha2 code that appears in the Geonames database (<https://www.geonames.org/countries/>). The disciplinary perspective is established using the five main research fields used in the Leiden Ranking classification (<https://www.leidenranking.com/information/fields>).

4. Results

In this section, the main results of the exploratory analysis are presented, organized by the research questions introduced above.

What is the number and share of African publications reporting funding? Are there differences across African countries?

A total of 867,944 publications with at least one African author has been identified, of which 208,646 publications included funding information (24% of the total). Figure 1 shows the share of publications reporting funding across African countries.

Figure 1: African countries by their share of publications with funding.

Who are the main funders in Africa? How do their funded publications behave in terms of collaboration patterns?

Table 1 presents the top 40 main funders in Africa by the number of publications in the continent reporting them as funders. Column 'Pubs' captures the total number of publications that report funding from each of the funders (for reasons of simplicity, full counting is applied, so if a publication has more than one funder, it is counted for each funder). Column '% collab' captures the percentage of publications of each funder that involves some degree of collaboration (i.e., having authors from more than one affiliation), while column '% int collab' shows the percentage of publications involving international collaboration (i.e., having authors from more than one country).

Table 1. Top 40 main funders in Africa in Dimensions. Period: 2010-2021. Funding organizations from Africa in italics/bold.

Funder	Country (headquarters)	Continent	Pubs	% collab	% int collab
<i>National Research Foundation (NRF)</i>	<i>South Africa</i>	<i>Africa</i>	36429	60.50%	43.49%
National Institutes of Health (NIH)	USA	North America	29277	95.34%	92.23%
European Commission (EC)	Belgium	Europe	17879	94.93%	92.77%
Wellcome Trust	United Kingdom	Europe	11739	94.94%	90.60%
National Natural Science Foundation of China (NSFC)	China	Asia	10416	99.54%	99.38%
Medical Research Council (MRC)	United Kingdom	Europe	9871	95.83%	93.18%
<i>Department of Science and Technology (DST)</i>	<i>South Africa</i>	<i>Africa</i>	7681	66.27%	47.60%
Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation	USA	North America	7408	96.13%	93.35%
Japan Society for the Promotion of Science (JSPS)	Japan	Asia	6400	99.36%	99.25%
Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG)	Germany	Europe	6288	98.30%	97.63%
<i>South African Medical Research Council (SAMRC)</i>	<i>South Africa</i>	<i>Africa</i>	5824	76.41%	55.77%
World Health Organization (WHO)	Switzerland	Europe	5408	92.29%	86.76%
French National Centre for Scientific Research (CNRS)	France	Europe	5105	97.71%	97.02%
Ministry of Economy, Industry and Competitiveness	Spain	Europe	5087	99.25%	99.06%
<i>Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research</i>	<i>Tunisia</i>	<i>Africa</i>	5063	70.97%	56.23%
European Research Council (ERC)	Belgium	Europe	4977	98.98%	98.69%
Ministry of Science and Technology of the People's Republic of China	China	Asia	4544	99.78%	99.78%
Directorate for Mathematical & Physical Sciences (NSF)	USA	North America	4434	99.71%	99.59%
United States Agency for International Development	USA	North America	4430	95.26%	92.42%
Agence Nationale de la Recherche (ANR)	France	Europe	4323	96.67%	96.23%
Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBWF)	Germany	Europe	4206	98.95%	98.29%
Science and Technology Facilities Council	United Kingdom	Europe	4062	99.51%	99.31%
Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF)	Switzerland	Europe	3966	98.39%	97.96%
United States Department of Energy	USA	North America	3660	99.67%	99.48%
National Science Foundation (NSF)	USA	North America	3574	99.02%	98.60%
National Council for Scientific and Technological Development (CNPq)	Brazil	South America	3386	99.73%	99.70%
Natural Sciences and Engineering Research Council (NERC)	Canada	North America	3273	99.54%	99.18%
Alexander von Humboldt Foundation	Germany	Europe	3266	94.24%	90.75%
Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT)	Portugal	Europe	3261	99.39%	99.26%
German Academic Exchange Service	Germany	Europe	3192	90.98%	85.46%
Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC)	USA	North America	3082	96.66%	90.91%
Department of Health and Social Care	United Kingdom	Europe	3056	98.85%	97.74%
Chinese Academy of Sciences (CAS)	China	Asia	2907	99.38%	98.83%
Dutch Research Council (NWO)	Netherlands	Europe	2659	98.16%	96.65%
Natural Environment Research Council (NERC)	United Kingdom	Europe	2597	98.04%	96.57%
National Research Foundation of Korea	South Korea	Asia	2593	97.07%	95.37%
<i>Science and Technology Development Fund (STDF)</i>	<i>Egypt</i>	<i>Africa</i>	2525	69.74%	44.99%
National Institute for Health and Care Research (NIHR)	United Kingdom	Europe	2461	99.19%	98.50%
São Paulo Research Foundation (FAPESP)	Brazil	South America	2321	99.91%	99.83%
Biotechnology and Biological Sciences Research Council (BBSRC)	United Kingdom	Europe	2306	98.22%	97.53%

What is the overall disciplinary presence of funding and funders on the continent? Are top funders specialized in some disciplines?

With these research questions we turn our attention to the presence and distribution of publications with funding information across the five major fields of science. Figure 2 reports the share of publications with funding information for each discipline. The largest share of African publications reporting funding is shown for the Life and earth sciences (34%), followed by the Biomedical and health sciences (28%) and the Physical sciences and engineering (26%).

Publications from the Social sciences and humanities (11%) as well as Mathematics and computer science (11%) feature less funding information. This suggests that these two fields are relatively underfunded in Africa.

Comparing these numbers with the whole world (orange bars), *Physical sciences and engineering* and *Mathematics and computer science* stand out, exhibiting substantially lower shares of publications with funding when compared to the world. African publications in *Physical sciences and engineering* almost half as often include funding information as could be expected based on the world share (26% Africa vs. 46% world); while for *Mathematics and computer science* funding information is almost three times less often included compared to the world average (11% Africa vs. 31% world).

Figure 2: Share of African publications (blue) with funding (vs. non-funded) by main (Leiden Ranking) fields of science – compared to the World (orange).

Figure 3 below shows the disciplinary profile of the publications funded by the five main non-African funders on the continent. For context, the overall distribution across fields of all African publications funded has been added as well.

The first observation based on Figure 3 is that African-funded publications overall have a strong concentration in the *Biomedical & health sciences*, with almost half of all funded publications classified in this field. This is followed by the *Life & earth sciences* and *Physical sciences &*

engineering. Mathematics & computer sciences and *Social sciences & humanities* both take a small share.

Figure 3: Share of publications funded by a selection of main funders' main fields of science.

Figure 3 shows that the main non-African funders funding research in Africa exhibit quite diverse thematic profiles. The Wellcome Trust, the National Institutes of Health and the Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation have a very strong focus on *Biomedical & health sciences*, with the latter also exhibiting some degree of focus on the *Life & earth sciences*. The European Commission and the National Natural Science Foundation of China both present a more multidisciplinary distribution, although the European Commission has a relatively stronger focus on *Life & earth sciences*, while the Chinese funding organization has a stronger orientation towards the *Physical sciences & engineering*.

5. Conclusions

This exploratory study presents an initial analysis of the funders and recipients of funding in Africa according to publication acknowledgements using Dimensions data. It is thus an update of the study by Kozma et al. (2018), with a more recent period (2010-2021) and a more inclusive database (Dimensions). Two observations confirm previous results:

- 1) The north-south divide in Africa regarding the funding reported in scientific publications is observed again. Large North-African countries like Egypt, Nigeria, Tunisia, Morocco, Algeria and Ethiopia present substantially lower shares of publications with funding information, usually below 20% of all publications. A similar result was observed for some of these countries by El-Ouahi (2024), using the Web of Science database. According to El-Ouahi, these low levels of funding sources mentioned in publications can be associated with block funding structures, in which lecturers or researchers are funded by universities or their governments without

necessarily reporting them as funders in their publications. This is an aspect deserving more attention in future studies.

- 2) International funders have a strong presence in the African continent. Funders like the European Commission, the NIH, the Wellcome Trust, the Chinese National Natural Science Foundation, or the Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation dominate the funding landscape. Also, publications funded by these international organizations are usually associated with internationally collaborative publications, suggesting a collaborative linkage between researchers from the countries of the funders and African researchers.

Additionally, the disciplinary analysis shows a stronger presence of funding information reported in publications from the disciplines of *Biomedical & health sciences* and *Life and earth sciences*, while the production in *Physical sciences & engineering* shows much lower shares of funding as compared with what is observed globally.

Our results also show the differentiated topical interests of international funders, with some of the main funders (NIH, Wellcome Trust, and Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation) heavily focusing on biomedical research, while the European Commission or the National Natural Science Foundation of China having a stronger focus on life and earth sciences, and physics and engineering respectively. Such differentiated patterns open the question of their role in setting the disciplinary research agenda in the continent and may suggest a need for more coordinated strategies in order to find a balance, e.g., by considering relatively under-funded fields like social sciences and humanities, or mathematics and computer sciences.

In terms of future research, a central part will be to analyse the flows of funding between sending and receiving countries and organizations. Dimensions data provides detailed information on grants, such as funding amounts, but also the recipients of grants (including the grantees and their respective affiliations) beyond just funding acknowledgements found on publications. Future work will have to leverage this information for a more complete picture of the science funding landscape in Africa.

Author contributions

Writing – original draft: IR, JD; writing – review & editing: all; conceptualization: all; data curation: JD & JvH; formal analysis: JD, JvH, & RC; funding acquisition: IR, RC, CdB; project management: CdB; supervision: IR & RC.

Competing interests

No competing interests.

Funding information

This work was carried out with the aid of a grant from the International Development Research Centre (IDRC), Ottawa, Canada. The views expressed herein do not necessarily represent those of IDRC or its Board of Governors. Rodrigo Costas is partially funded by the South African DSI-NRF Centre of Excellence in Scientometrics and Science, Technology and Innovation Policy (SciSTIP).

References

Álvarez-Bornstein, B., & Montesi, M. (2020). Funding acknowledgements in scientific publications: A literature review. *Research Evaluation*, 29(4). <https://doi.org/10.1093/reseval/rvaa038>

Ciarli, T., Aldoh, A. M. A. A., Arora, S., Arza, V., Asinsten, J., Assa, J., Chataway, J., Colonna, A., Confraria, H., Kombo, P. N., Mittal, N., Mulgan, G., Ndege, N., Noyons, E., Ouma-Mugabe, J., Bhuvana, N., Rafols, I., Steenmans, I., Stirling, A., ... Yegros, A. (2022). Changing Directions: Steering science, technology and innovation towards the Sustainable Development Goals (Version 1). University of Sussex. <https://hdl.handle.net/10779/uos.23492681.v1>

Ciarli, T., & Ràfols, I. (2019). The relation between research priorities and societal demands: The case of rice. *Research Policy*, 48(4). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2018.10.027>

El-Ouahi, J. (2024). Research funding in the Middle East and North Africa: analyses of acknowledgments in scientific publications indexed in the Web of Science (2008–2021). *Scientometrics*, 129. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-024-04983-8>

Herzog, C., Hook, D., & Konkiel, S. (2020). Dimensions: Bringing down barriers between scientometricians and data. *Quantitative Science Studies*, 1(1), 387–395.

Kokol, P., & Vošner, H.B. (2018). Discrepancies among Scopus, Web of Science, and PubMed coverage of funding information in medical journal articles. *Journal of the Medical Library Association*, 106(1). <https://doi.org/10.5195/jmla.2018.181>

Kozma, C., Calero Medina, C., & Costas, R. (2018). Research funding landscapes in Africa. In C. Beaudry, J. Mouton, & H. Prozesky (Eds.), *The Next Generation of Scientists in Africa* (pp. 26–42). African Minds. https://muse.jhu.edu/pub/362/edited_volume/chapter/2267598

Lepori, B., Jongbloed, B., & Hicks, D. (2023). Introduction to the Handbook of Public Funding of Research: Understanding vertical and horizontal complexities. In B. Lepori, B. Jongbloed, & D. Hicks (Eds.), *Handbook of Public Funding of Research* (pp. 1–19). Edward Elgar Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.4337/9781800883086.00005>

Liu, W., Tang, L. & Hu, G. (2020). Funding information in Web of Science: an updated overview. *Scientometrics*, 122. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-020-03362-3>

Paul-Hus, A., Desrochers, N. & Costas, R. (2016). Characterization, description, and considerations for the use of funding acknowledgement data in Web of Science. *Scientometrics*, 108. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-016-1953-y>

Sarewitz, D., & Pielke, R. A. (2007). The neglected heart of science policy: Reconciling supply of and demand for science. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 10(1). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2006.10.001>

Vessuri, H. (2017). From Science as “Development Assistance” to “Global Philanthropy”. In D. Tyfield, R. Lave, S. Randalls, & C. Thorpe (Eds.), *The Routledge Handbook of the Political Economy of Science* (1st ed., pp. 405–415). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315685397-36>